

Type of knowledge indication	Knowledge Indication	Level of application (0-3)
Conceptual Knowledge	Use scientific concepts	The level of use of scientific concepts (poor-1/ suitable-2 rich-3)
Conceptual Knowledge	Explain the phenomena	The level of scientific explanation (simple - 1 without reasoning, extended - 2 including reasoning, sophisticated - 3 with reasoning and examples).
Conceptual knowledge	Identify relations	The level of identification of relationships (no identification-0/ identification of low-order relations-1 / identification of high-order relations-2/ identification of relation on relation-3
Knowledge Representation	Describe +Represent relations on graph	Level of graphical representation of the knowledge (no representation-0/ representation of one low-order relations-1/ representation of two or more low-order relations -2/ representation of relations over a high-order relations-3 (relation vs. relations)
MSK-Procedural knowledge	Use the cognitive Actions for mapping -How	The level of use of cognitive operations coding, inference, mapping - there was no

		explicit use -0 there was explicit use -1
MSK + Declarative knowledge	When Mention the skill name	Explicit identification level (when) of the skill is incorrect - 0 / true for one skill - 1 / true for two skills - 2, level of explicit identification for 3 skills - 3)
MSK—conditional knowledge	Justify Why	Considerations in the application of the skill (There is no justification 0/ there is a suitable justification for one skill- 1/ there is a suitable justification for 2 skills- 2, there is a suitable justification for 3 skills)
Skill Application		Appropriate application of RRs - (no match application -0 / partial application -1 recognized a RR pattern in identifying the problem but did not know how to apply or vice versa. Full application recognized a pattern and knew how to apply it (in a scientific explanation of the problem solution -2)